

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Neuroactive molecule engagement during TNBC resistance.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Peptide *PYY2* was among those most abundantly increased during resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro*. We also found adrenoceptor *ADRA1D* and adrenomedullin *ADM2* activation during resistance to chemotherapy.